

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for awarding a fellowship to one of the authors (S.B.), and to U.G.C., New Delhi, for financial assistance to the other (M.N.A.).

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Studies on Oxadiazole. Part-VIII. Preparation and Antimicrobial Activity of *p,p'*-Bis(2-substituted-benzoylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone

M. A. SHAHSAFI, N. H. MESHKATALSADAT

and

HANSA PAREKH*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University,
Rajkot-360 005

Manuscript received 11 February 1987, revised 30 November 1987,
accepted 2 December 1987

In view of various biological activities¹ 1,3,4-oxadiazoles, their derivatives of type 1 were prepared by condensing dapsone with monochloromethyl acetate in presence of dimethylformamide. The ester so formed was converted to the corresponding hydrazide by treatment of hydrazine hydrate. The constitution of the product was supported by ir and nmr spectral data. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity.

1
R = Aryl

Experimental

Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu 435 spectrophotometer and nmr spectra on a EM-360 (60 MHz) spectrometer using DMSO-D₆.

p,p'-Bis(carbomethoxymethylamino)diphenylsulphone : *p,p'*-Diaminodiphenylsulphone (0.01 mol)

in dimethylformamide (30 ml) was added to methyl chloroacetate (0.02 ml) and contents were refluxed for 3 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from dimethylformamide, (90%), m.p. 155° (Found : C, 55.02 ; H, 5.07 ; N, 7.10. C₁₈H₂₀O₆N₂S calcd. for : C, 55.10 ; H, 5.10 ; N, 7.14%).

p,p'-Bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone : A mixture of *p,p'*-(carbomethoxymethylamino)diphenylsulphone (0.01 mol), ethanol (95%) and hydrazine hydrate (100%, 0.02 mol) was refluxed for 36 h. Ethanol was then removed and the product was isolated and crystallised from dimethylformamide, (83%), m.p. 98° (Found : C, 48.88 ; H, 5.08 ; N, 21.37. C₁₈H₂₀O₄N₆S calcd. for : (C, 48.97 ; H, 5.10 ; N, 21.42%).

p,p'-Bis(2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone : A mixture of *p,p'*-bis(hydrazinocarbonylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone (0.01 mol), methanol (30 ml) and cyanogen bromide (0.02 mol) was refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and neutralised with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (67%), m.p. 132° (Found : C, 48.82 ; H, 4.04 ; N, 24.30. C₁₈H₁₈O₄N₈S calcd. for : C, 48.86 ; H, 4.07 ; N, 25.33%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350, (N-H str.), 1 620 (NH def.), 1 395 (S=O asym. str.), 1 180 (S=O sym. str.), 1 685 (C=N str.) and 1 140 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C str.).

p,p'-Bis(2-benzoylamino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone : A mixture of benzoic acid (0.01 mol), thionyl chloride (0.01 mol) in dioxan (40 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. Excess thionyl chloride was removed by distillation. The product obtained was then refluxed with *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone in dioxan (20 ml) with 2-3 drops of pyridine for further 2 h. The product was isolated and crystallised from methanol, (75%), m.p. 180° (Found : C, 59.01 ; H, 3.98 ; N, 21.10. C₃₂H₂₆O₆N₈S calcd. for : C, 59.07 ; H, 4.00 ; N, 17.23%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 350 (NH str.), 1 690 (amide-I), 1 510 (amide-II), 1 290 (amide-III), 1 620 (C=N str.), 1 080 (C-O-C str.), 1 340 (S=O asym. str.) and 1 140 cm⁻¹ (S=O sym. str.) ; δ 7.88 (m, ArH) and 2.45 (s, CH₂).

Similarly other aromatic acid chlorides were condensed with *p,p'*-bis(2-amino-1,3,4-oxadiazol-5-ylmethylamino)diphenylsulphone. Physical data of the products are recorded in Table 1.

Antimicrobial activity : 1,3,4-Oxadiazoles (1) were screened for their antibacterial and antifungal activity using cup-plate method². The testing was carried

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF *p,p'*-BIS(SUBSTITUTED-BENZOYLAMINO-1,3,4-OXADIAZOL-5-YLMETHYL-AMINO)DIPHENYLSULPHONES*

R	Mol. formula	M.p. °C	Yield %
Phenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₄ S	180	75
<i>o</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	145	73
<i>m</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	215	80
<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₄ S	232	73
2,4-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄ S	236	62
2,6-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄ S	272	54
3,5-Dihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₄ S	222	58
3,4,5-Trihydroxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₀ O ₅ N ₄ S	253	66
<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ SCl	186	77
<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ SCl	138	82
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ SCl	235	54
<i>o</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ S	325	60
<i>m</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ S	239	72
<i>p</i> -Aminophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₅ O ₂ N ₄ S	360	70
3-Pyridyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ S	212	82
4-Pyridyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₄ S	238	73
2-Hydroxy-3,5-dinitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₀ O ₄ N ₆ S	208	69
1-Hydroxy-2-naphthyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	190	73
2-Hydroxy-3-naphthyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₄ S	183	82
<i>o</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ S	176	65
<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ S	212	80
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ S	192	72
3,5-Dinitrophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₆ S	238	68
<i>o</i> -Acetyloxyphenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₄ S	218	60
Cinnamyl	C ₂₆ H ₁₈ O ₂ N ₄ S	158	64
β -Phenethylcinnamyl	C ₂₈ H ₂₀ O ₂ N ₄ S	360	81
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	C ₂₂ H ₁₃ O ₂ N ₄ SB ₂	208	79
Benzyl	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ O ₂ N ₄ S	228	68
Benzylaminomethyl	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ O ₂ N ₄ S	176	70

*Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained.

out at a concentration of 100 μ g using gram-positive (*Staphylococcus aureus*, *S. citrus*) and gram-negative (*Escherichia coli*, *Salmonella typhosa*) bacteria. The antifungal testing was carried out against *Aspergillus niger*, *Neurospora cressa*. The antimicrobial activity of the compounds was compared with chloramphenicol, penicillin G, penicillin K and streptomycin at the same concentration level. It was observed that most of the compounds showed moderate activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

Maximum activity was observed in case of compounds having R = *m*-chlorophenyl, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-hydroxyphenyl and benzylaminomethyl against *S. citrus* and good activity against *A. niger* for compounds having R = 3-pyridyl, 4-pyridyl, 3,4,5-trihydroxyphenyl, 3,5-dihydroxyphenyl, *o*-acetyloxyphenyl and *p*-nitrophenyl.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. A. R. Parikh, Professor and Head, Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot, for facilities and also to the Ministry of Higher Education, Government of Iran, Tehran, for research scholarship to two of them (M.A.S and M.H.M.).

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Studies on 4-Thiazolidinones. Part-VI. Synthesis and Antimicrobial activity of 2-Aryl-3-(2',4'-dibutylamino-*s*-triazin-6'-yl)-5-H/methyl/carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinones

LINA MEHTA and HANSA PAREKH*

Department of Chemistry, Saurashtra University, Rajkot-360 005

Manuscript received 27 July 1987, accepted 4 November 1987

4-Thiazolidinones are associated with various kinds of biological activities¹. *s*-Triazine derivatives also possess various biological activities². In order to synthesise more active drugs, we have prepared 4-thiazolidinone derivatives of type 1 by the action of thioglycolic acid, thiolactic acid and thiomalic acid on Schiff bases obtained by

1, R = Aryl, X = H/CH₃/OH, COOH

condensing 2,4-dibutylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine with different aromatic aldehydes. The constitution of the product was supported by its spectral study. The products were screened for antimicrobial activity.

Experimental

M.p.s. are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer.

2,4-Dibutylamino-6-amino-*s*-triazine: 2,4-Dibutylamino-6-chloro-*s*-triazine³ (0.01 mol) in dioxane was treated with ammonia (0.01 mol) at 80–90° for 1.5 h. The product was isolated and crystallised, (80%), m.p. 203° (Found: C, 55.31; H, 8.99; N, 35.11. C₁₁H₂₂N₆ requires: C, 55.46; H, 9.24; N, 35.3%).